

GEOLOCATED LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS AND CAPACITY BUILDING FOR TAILORED SUPPORT IN THE CONTEXT OF AN OPEN WEB INDEX

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Abstract

This paper addresses the requirements and constraints of learning and capacity building and its tailored support in the context of the Open Search Foundation. Special focus is the identification of a future road map for temporal and spatial requirements in the context of capacity building and learning environments with tailored information for target groups on one side and an Open Web Index with spatial decision support layers as public goods and a transparent, accessible infrastructure, that is free of charge to all people and allows the single user and the educational system to protect the learner for undesired profiling on the other side. Furthermore, spatial allocation of searchable content for learning and capacity building contributes to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the basic principle of “Think Globally - Act Locally”.

LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS AND CAPACITY BUILDING

At first, we address the link between Capacity Building and learning environments. Joint requirements for tailored spatial support through locally or regionally relevant search results leads to Spatial Decision Support Layers (SDSL) as deliverable for an Open Web Index (OWI). Learning environments and capacity building are retrievable for the geolocation of capacity builders with an OWI. In the following, we define both terms.

Capacity Building

Capacity building or development is widely understood as a process of strengthening skills, competencies and development of abilities to solve problems, set and achieve objectives on individual, organizations and society level (United Nations, 2006, [1]). Acknowledging the importance of empowerment of local communities reaching the 2030 Agenda of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; United Nations, 2015, [2]), community capacity building includes the aspect of active involvement and long-term ownership of measures and processes communities need

to survive and adapt to changing environments (Simmons et al., 2011, [3]) and is closely linked with the concept of leaving no one behind (UNDP, 2018, [4]).

Building of local capacities in form of technical, organizational, advocacy skills on individual and community levels to guarantee active involvement in decision making processes thus also includes the use of a local- and target group specific learning environment that can strongly be supported by the use of an OWI.

Learning Environments

The *pedagogical understanding* of a learning environment is primarily concerned with providing the children with a pleasant learning atmosphere, i.e. a situation in which they feel safe, accepted, respected and taken seriously (Krauthausen, 2018, [5]).

A different understanding of a learning environment refers to the *methodological-organizational arrangement*, e.g. a child-friendly design of the learning space (e.g. the classroom). This can affect the learning atmosphere and thus the learning process and learning outcomes (Krauthausen, 2018, [5]).

This paper focuses primarily on the *substantive understanding of learning environments*, whereby a learning environment is understood as an extension of the usual term task, essentially a work situation as a whole, which should enable and support active discovery and social learning (Wollring, 2008, [6]).

In the following five examples of learning environments that can contribute to worldwide capacity building through an OWI are briefly described.

*This template is closely based on the OpenDocument template courtesy of JACoW (<http://jacow.org>)

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1 - Celestial Bodies – Learning Environment

Determination of the apparent motion of the sun, moon and other celestial bodies is mentioned as an example because the learning environment addresses regional differences of positions of stars. To analyze the apparent motion of celestial bodies allows to operate spatial geometry on different mathematical levels in a multidisciplinary context and is therefore particularly suitable for interdisciplinary projects. The basic considerations here are of a global nature. However, the actual apparent motion depends strongly on the latitude of the observer. This has an influence on all kinds of everyday phenomena such as the sun's rise and set, the length of the day, etc. Rules for the determination of the time by means of the stars are additionally dependent on the longitude of the observer. (This example is contributed by Mutfried Hartmann.)

2 - Real-World Laboratory: Queichland

The “Reallabor Queichland” is mentioned as an example because it allows local interaction with the environment and addresses regional characteristics. The Real-World Laboratory in Landau, Germany, focuses on educational content, citizen participation and the development of a carrierless educational landscape on a green area of 7 hectares, the Queichpark. (This example is contributed by Marc B. Rieger and Björn Risch.)

3 - Geocaching-Project

Geocaching-Project is mentioned as an example because geocaches and the availability of these geocaches are encoded in a spatial access map. In a geocaching seminar, teacher trainees develop a local geocaching as multi-cache with mathematical tasks and puzzles on the topic of city history for school classes' excursions into the city. (This example is contributed by Melanie Platz.)

4 - Mathematical Environmental Lab

The mathematical environmental lab is mentioned as an example for how global environmental risk maps define spatial risks and allow for locally relevant risk mitigation activities for capacity building. The Mathematical Environmental Lab is an extra-curricular place of learning at the University of Koblenz-Landau. In this lab highly gifted pupils, students obtaining a teacher profession in mathematics and students of environmental science work together in small groups to solve project orientated questions, mostly in the field of an environmental problem with a temporal and spatial dimension. The mathematical environmental lab links spatial decision support layers as deliverable for environmental problems (capacity building) with learning environments about mathematical representation of risk and resources. (This example is contributed by Jörg Rapp and Melanie Platz.)

5 - Geolocation & Health Issues

Remote sensing imagery and advanced image analysis methods contribute to global monitoring tasks (e.g.

SDGs). The conditions of forests and the environmental conditions of habitats can be detected with remote sensing by conducting a multi-scale approach for the delineation or e.g. by application of NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) of plants or monitoring of air pollution. The example is mentioned because it allows locally applicable interventions for assessment and conservation of habitats and landscapes. The multi-spectral satellite imagery can contribute to assessment of greenhouse gas storage. Precision farming reduces the amount of applied agrochemicals with impact on public health and environmental health (Auernhammer, 2001, [7]). (This example is contributed by Barbara Riedler and Jörg Rapp.)

Think Globally – Act Locally

We consider the concept of “Think Globally - Act Locally” (Kefalas, 1998, [8]) from the angle of capacity building and learning. Learn to act locally requires the information that is tailored for the region or location, where the user is active. Capacity building in the context of global challenges e.g. global health, global sustainability, climate change and the consequences takes into account that the options for risk mitigation are diverse and resources for risk mitigation are heterogeneous in different regions. Also, cultural and social requirements and constraints have an impact on local action for risk mitigation. The demand for tailored information for the geolocation and the requirement of an OWI to be transparent how the geographically tailored information is generated from the OWI creates some specification for the OWI and its deliverers. This will lead to the SDSL as a content element of a search engine, that allows to create tailored filtering on the client side.

WHY TAILORED INFORMATION FOR LEARNING AND CAPACITY BUILDING?

Capacity building and learning environments incorporate local and regional requirements and constraints (prerequisites of the learner, local and regional, geographical, social, legal, cultural and health related requirements and constraints, among others).

SDSLs define how specific content elements, learning objects or properties are relevant for the specific geolocation or region. The OWI provides a SDSL with a digital signature of the generator (e.g. a local initiative, World Health Organization, educational institute or NGO for capacity building and training events).

The digital signature is necessary that the users can trust that the data was delivered by a respective organization or institute and the learner or teacher can decide, if they trust the information in the SDSL or not.

The personalization can be performed by the teacher/trainer or by the learner and the learning process includes

the capacity building for teachers, trainers or learners to perform the filtering according to objectives of learning and capacity building. Nevertheless, the basic principle of a decision support layer as a deliverable for an OWI must be incorporated into a search engine.

Focusing the generator side of a SDSL and a participatory maintenance of an OWI, the workflow from a research question of a project towards an existing SDSL is driven by a research project as usual. There is no difference from other research projects in the educational domain. The outputs of a research project are not only scientific papers but also SDSLs, that define how relevant a specific learning resource is for a geographical location and environment. The product will be digitally signed by the research institute (Pariser, 2012, [9]), so that it is transparent who created the information filter and scientific standards allow to reconstruct the local and regional relevance for the learning resources or capacity building resource. Transparency means, that the public and the scientific community will be able to cross-check and perform the methodology of an institute or organization. Furthermore, transparency of SDSL generation requires also the right of another, second organization to adapt the methodology of the first organization and to use a tailored new SDSL for a different purpose. The alteration of the SDSL by the second organization makes the digital signature of the first organization invalid. If the institution wants to publish the SDSL in the OWI the SDSL must be digitally signed before publishing the SDSL in the OWI. The locally required information can be filtered by trusted institutions or organizations. The implementation of filtering and the adaptation to the requirements and constraints of learners or the target groups are performed on the side of the decision makers, trainers or teachers and not by the search engine itself.

Capacity building and learning in educational institutions (e.g. schools, universities) have in common that they both take into account that learning requires adaptation to the target group and to the geographic location and environment where the target group is situated.

For example, the target group could think globally in terms of the SDGs (United Nations, 2015, [2]), and the learners and capacity builders would be willing to address e.g. SDG3 – Good health and well-being. Risk mitigation according to the exposure to agrochemicals could lead to farming and efficient use of less agrochemicals by keeping the same harvest yield or by additional information of introduction of organic farming. The key word “heavy metals” may lead also to other natural resources of exposure to heavy metals that add to the risk. The OWI could make the connection between disciplines visible by using the SDSL of heavy metal in regions of volcanic activity.

IT resource requirements for contribution to an OWI must allow active contributions to the OWI in a cross-

disciplinary approach with digital signature of authors. Thus, social sciences must be able to add a digitally signed SDSL to the OWI. Contributions to the OWI are not only determined by Web Crawlers. Rural regions have different requirements and constraints and if social sciences identify regional differences and create a SDSL as a research outcome then this social and cultural SDSL can be used for local and regional decision making, learning and capacity building programs.

Filter bubbles (Pariser, 2012, [9]) are already influencing their own search queries, but most users are unaware of the fact. They erroneously assume that everyone gets the same information and the prioritization of the content in the search engine reflects more or less the global relevance of the topic.

An OWI decomposes the Web Index, that maps “Keywords” to “Web Content” that is associated to the keyword from the filtering for the target group. Decomposition of OWI and the filtering mechanism requires capacity building for the teachers, trainers, coaches, public health workers, to maintain, generate and adapt a profile for themselves and the target group of learners or the community they work in and work for.

GENERATION OF USER PROFILE AND FILTERING

In the previous sections we discussed the filter mechanism, that must be decomposed from the Black Box of commercial search engines. If we decompose that from the search engine itself, it is necessary to define how the filtering can be performed in a transparent way from clients that perform the information retrieval with the OWI.

We analyze the possible options

- Set profile manual for yourself (is ALWAYS possible).
- Automated profile through geolocation alone (is ALWAYS possible, can be switched off). The geolocation filtering can also be set manually for another location (e. g. refugee camp or a *Real-World Laboratory* – see example 2 – as learning environment, where the user is currently not located but he/she is planning for that location).
- Required option (ALWAYS): Information retrieval without profiling of the user. Switch off of profile filtering has the advantage to address the retrieval geographically independent of a global scale. No priority of regional search results defines also the local profile for the information retrieval. Also allowing retrieval beyond the own expertise as filter mechanism enables the discovery of new facts and additional feasible measures.

In an interdisciplinary context capacity building and learning environments have commonalities. To see this

connection between capacity building and learning environments, capacity builders, educators and researchers might not see the link of those domains in mutual way. In this context we identify these commonalities to derive future requirements for the OWI. We distinguish between formal and non-formal education. While formal education is traditional education in pre-school, schools, colleges and universities (Learning Environments), non-formal education often focuses on lifelong learning with the aim of access to education for all (Capacity Building). It is typically provided in form of workshops or short courses and could for example include training of farm-workers that might be even illiterate (see example 5 - *Geolocation & Health Issues*).

GEOLOCATION FOR WEB CONTENT - SDSL

Web content may be assigned or refer to specific geolocations. Users might be interested in accessing information via an OWI, that are relevant for their current geolocation or users select a specific geolocation or area of interest for the research query. A geographical reference allows the assignment of content items (text, audio, video, animations, simulations, questionnaires, ...) to one or more locations which are addressed by the content itself. This approach is connected to the management of local resources and the spatial support of decision-making processes which in turn is based on collecting and/or providing data for a certain geographical region.

In this paper joint requirements of Capacity Building and learning environments for tailored spatial support through locally or regionally relevant search results are focused, which leads to SDSLs as deliverable for an OWI. The emergence of an SDSL is thus grounded on the basic principle that geographic information can be assigned and represented as a spatial assignment layer (SAL) of key properties on a global scale in comparison to extracted geospatial features from content and assignment of a spatial keyword to crawled web content. The SALs are a generalized approach of assigning spatial keywords (Europe, Switzerland, Berlin or 48°14'05"N 16°25'01"E) to a web content. In this context SALs refer for example to ecotoxicological risks and assignment of peer-reviewed journals to the geographic locations on that topic.

The demands of specific areas can be evaluated locally or regionally at a specific geolocation additionally to a complete risk map. The GIS-based generation of a SAL is required for quality assured informed decision making in e.g. the health-domain. Information management needs a transparent, reproducible assignment of SALs.

The SAL can be logically combined like the keywords "*water AND sanitation*" in a classical research query. In contrast to server profiles of users with geographical preferences a SAL is independent of user preferences. The SAL is based on scientific evidence and spatial

representation can be combined logically by spatial Fuzzy-Logic on a global scale or tailored to the geolocation of the user.

These SALs are combined with a spatial quality of information that allows decision makers to assess the trust to the mapped content by the spatial quality of information and by the scientific resources the SAL is based on.

For transparency the organizational/ institutional origin can be identified. The SAL and the spatial quality of information is dynamically maintained by scientific institutions. New scientific evidences alter the spatial quality of information according to the area of reference.

Areas may be explicitly mentioned with latitude/longitude in a web content (e.g. CERN - Wikipedia Article with Geolocation, [10]) or may be encoded in the text (e.g. "*CERN in Geneva*" is mapped to latitude/longitude automatically Lat: 35.051790 Long: -77.021880) and extracted and assigned automatically to a geolocation or region.

REQUIREMENTS AND CONSTRAINTS OF SDSLS: AN EXAMPLE

With the following example of Real-World Laboratories (see example 2 - *Real-World Laboratory: Queichland*), we visualize the requirements and constraints for SDSLs as deliverable of an OWI.

As educational venues, Real-World Laboratories represent an ideal basis for education for sustainable development in an authentic learning environment. In the Queichland Real-World Laboratory, authentic learning offerings (Risch et al., 2019, [11]) on environmental contexts are developed and offered in a dialogue between science, educational institutions and civil society. The contents refer to SDGs 6 ("Clean Water"), 13 ("Climate Protection") and 15 ("Living on Land").

Before visiting an out-of-school learning location, it is desirable that interested parties can find out about the possibilities of the learning location by means of a search engine. During the stay at the learning location, it is helpful if the visitors can call up the information provided by means of QR codes or augmented reality on their smartphones (e.g. geolocation-specific data on the local natural conditions). This not only promotes a deeper understanding of the natural processes on site, but also enables access to specific learning materials.

In the Queichpark, the area of the Real-World Laboratory Queichland, it would be useful for visitors to be able to retrieve up-to-date information on renaturation processes, chemical and biological data of the river Queich (localization) or the habitats of locally occurring animals and insects in the search results, for example. Such a function would also make it possible to assign

required regional environmental characteristics of the learning content to multiple global locations that share the same characteristics. The SDSL defines the matching quality of the local design for other regions.

A simple and clear handling of a self-controlled indexing of the materials would be important for the functionality. This should enable educational institutions to provide educational content with keywords for an optimal search. A kind of educational interface would also be desirable, i. e. a front-end for teachers and students to integrate educational content into the search selection. For this purpose, it would also be desirable to be able to manually keyword GPS coordinates of specific natural phenomena so that interested parties could already be shown a possible pre-selection. An example: In the Queichpark, the river Queich was freed from its concrete riverbed and now meanders freely across the area in a tributary. Impact and sliding slopes are formed. If a learner now finds himself in a certain GPS quadrant in front of the impact slope of a meandering arm, the education front-end could already suggest search terms that indicate this. These search terms could be introduced by educational institutions to draw attention to learning content in the immediate vicinity of the user. With such possibilities a worldwide capacity building with indexed learning content would be possible. It could also simplify the implementation of Citizen Science approaches, as citizens can be made more aware of them. People can thus not only teach and learn locally, but also contribute directly to research and improvement of the environment. The methods and materials created individually or jointly by all participants are made available via open source software. Only in this way it is possible to provide all citizens with both a digital software infrastructure and associated editable digital learning content (Open Educational Resources, OER).

CONCLUSION

According to Capacity Building and learning environments we showed the requirement of tailored spatial decision support for search of relevant learning environments and Capacity Building material adapted to the region of application which leads to SDSLs as deliverable for an OWI.

SDSLs allow the tailoring on the client side with full control over the filter mechanism. This is in line with the constraint of an OWI, that the profiling and filtering is not applied on the server side. Furthermore, a SDSL must be regarded as deliverable of an OWI that is digitally signed e. g. from the issuing agency, university or research institute, so that users can select the SDSL from trusted organizations and build tailored decisions on that trusted information.

A scientifically managed resource of a microservice for domain-specific search queries (in this case for capacity building and learning with geolocated referencing of

digital content) is proposed as contribution to an OWI, which differs from a “traditional” web crawler in the following way:

In the scientifically managed approach, a scientific group fetches pages and analyzes the content for relevance for a specific scientific domain (e.g. with special focus on learning environments and Capacity Building material). The content of the pages is indexed according to relevance, quality, state of the art and geolocation, among others, and the scientific group signs the service with digital signature. Alteration of microservice/feed is versioned and a spatial assignment layer (SAL) can be created, which contributes to the development of SDSLs. The index allows to perform search query by apps and the individual application defines which microservice is integrated into the search query (e.g. CERN service only, etc.).

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